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Development and characterization of Microemulsion based system of Aceclofenac

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the present study was to incorporate poorly soluble Aceclofenac (ACF) into microemulsion based formulation. In present study microemulsion was prepared with 6% w/w Isopropyl Myristate (IPM), 27%w/w Tween 80 & 18%w/w PEG-400 as oil, surfactant & Cosurfactant respectively. The ratio of surfactant: cosurfactant was fixed at 4:1 on the basis of Ternary phase diagram. Microemulsion gel was prepared using 1% Carbopol 934 as a gelling agent. Optimized formulation was evaluated for drug content, zeta potential, droplet size, drug assay, pH, viscosity, in-vitro drug release profile and stability study. Globule size of optimize batch ACF 5 was found to be 11.52 ± 0.6 nm. In vitro release study had shown 25.55 ± 2.39 % drug release from microemulsion gel which was more compared to marketed product. Optimize batch ACF 5 was found stable throughout stability study for two months at different temperature (2-8°C & room temperature).

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Introduction

Now a day, pharmaceutical research is aimed at developing suitable drug delivery system to fulfill the therapeutic needs of the patient. The development of novel drug delivery should meet with the development of new chemical entities, where majority of the molecules discovered were hydrophobic in nature. In the thrust of developing new delivery systems, Microemulsion (ME) gained a prominence in the effective delivery of the hydrophobic drugs.^(1,2)

Aceclofenac [[[2-[(2,6-Dichlorophenyl)-amino]-acetyl]-oxy]-acetic acid is a Diclofenac Derivative of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID).^(3,4,5) NSAIDs are the most commonly used drugs to reduce pain and inflammation. Aceclofenac has been recommended orally for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthritis.⁽⁶⁾ It works by blocking the action of a substance in the body called cyclooxygenase.⁽⁷⁾

Most NSAIDs are weak acids, with a pKa of 3-5. They are absorbed well from the stomach and intestinal mucosa. They are highly protein-bound in plasma (typically >95%), usually to albumin, so that their volume of distribution typically approximates to plasma volume. Most NSAIDs are metabolized in the liver by oxidation and conjugation to inactive metabolites which are typically excreted in the urine, although some drugs are partially excreted in bile. Metabolism may be abnormal in certain disease states, and accumulation may occur even with normal dosage.^(8,9,10)

The topical application of NSAIDs has been widely explored in the treatment of several disorders (e.g. osteoarthritis) as an alternative route to overcome the adverse side effects associated with the oral and rectal routes of administration, including gastrointestinal intolerance.^(11,12,13) Several reports have shown that microemulsions represent promising vehicles for improving the delivery, efficacy and

bioavailability of several NSAIDs, such as ketoprofen, celecoxib, rofecoxib, aceclofenac, piroxicam, and diclofenac.^(14,15)

Microemulsions are thermodynamically stable, transparent, isotropic, low-viscosity colloidal dispersions consisting of oil and water stabilized by an interfacial film consisting of surfactant/co-surfactant. Microemulsions offer various advantages like thermodynamic stability, ability to entrap hydrophilic, hydrophobic therapeutic agents etc.^(16,17,18,19) These systems show the improved oral bioavailability due to enhanced solubility and permeability of the drug in the entire area of the gastro-intestinal tract.^(20,21) Enhanced dermal transport was observed with these deliveries in the transdermal drug delivery due to lipophilicity and improved permeation rate in presence of surfactants.^(22,23) Besides these obvious advantages, also involves less number of unit operations in the formulation development, which is more convenient for the manufacturers in terms of economy. In addition microemulsion induces change in the thermodynamic activity of drug they contain, modifying their partition co-efficient and thus favours penetration through stratum corneum.^(24,25) Furthermore its components (Surfactant & Co-surfactant) reduce the functional barrier of the stratum corneum.^(26,27)

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Materials

Aceclofenac was gifted by Relex Pharmaceutical (Baroda), Iso-propyl Myristate (IPM) – Suvidhinath Laboratories (Baroda), Tween 80 – National Chemicals (Baroda), Polyethylene Glycol 400(PEG 400) – Suvidhinath Laboratories, Carbopol 934 – Suvidhinath Laboratories, HPMC – Suvidhinath Laboratories. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Experimental ^(26,28,29,30)

Solubility determination:

Solubility of the Aceclofenac was determined in different oils such as Capmul MCM(C8), Labrafac PG, Labrafac lipophile, Oleic acid, Isopropyl myristate, Olive oil, Cotton seed oil and soyabean oil, surfactants such as Tween 80, Creamophore RH and Labrasol and cosurfactants such as polyethylene glycol 400, and Plurol oleique CC 497. Drug was added in excess to different oils, surfactants and cosurfactants and stirred for 24 hrs on magnetic stirrer.

After stirring, samples were centrifuged at 7500 rpm for 10 min and the drug in the supernatant was analyzed at λ_{\max} 276 nm after proper dilution with Methanol: DCM (4:6). Drug solubility data is shown in the Table 1.

Ternary Phase diagram:

Pseudo ternary phase diagram is a useful and important tool to study the phase behaviour of microemulsions. Pseudo ternary phase diagram is constructed to obtain the appropriate components and their concentration ranges that can result in large existence area of microemulsion. Once the appropriate microemulsion components are selected, ternary pseudo phase diagram is constructed to define the extent and nature of the microemulsion regions. To produce such diagrams, a large number of samples of different composition are prepared. The microemulsion region is initially delineated by its isotropic nature and low viscosity.

In this study, the Pseudo ternary phase diagrams of oil (Iso-propyl myristate), surfactant/co surfactant (Tween 80/ PEG 400) and water were developed by using water titration method to obtain the components' concentration ranges that can result in large existence area of microemulsion. Surfactant was blended with cosurfactant in fixed weight ratios (1:1, 2:1, 3:1, 4:1 and 5:1). For each phase diagram, the ratio of oil to the Smix was varied as 9:1, 8:2, 7:3,

6:4, 5:5, 4:6, 3:7, 2:8, 1:9 (w/w). Aliquots of each surfactant and cosurfactant mixture (Smix) were mixed with oil at room temperature with continuous stirring. Water was added drop wise to each oil-Smix mixture under vigorous stirring.

After equilibrium, the samples were visually checked and determined as being clear microemulsions or emulsions or gels. Results are shown in Table 2. Phase diagram was plotted based on readings which are shown in Figure 1.

Formulation of Microemulsion: ^(29,30,31)

Preparation of Aceclofenac loaded o/w Microemulsion was prepared by water titration method. Surfactant & Co-Surfactant were mixed in fixed ratio to oil followed by Aceclofenac. Sonication was performed in bathsonicated for 5 minutes to dissolve drug.

Required quantity of water was added dropwise with stirring. Allow the solution to form clear and transparent liquid which was microemulsion. Different batches of blank microemulsion formulation were prepared as shown in Table 3. Among them few batches with drug were prepared based on the transparency and physical observation as shown in Table 4.

Preparation of Aceclofenac loaded microemulsion Gel: ⁽³²⁾

Different concentration of Carbopol 934 (0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, 2% & 2.5%), HPMC K4 M (1%, 2% & 3%) and HPMC K100 (1%, 2% & 3%) were tried to prepare gel. Among them Carbopol 934 1.5 % gel was optimized for further process. In the small quantity of water, 1.5 % Carbopol 934 & 4.5% Propylene glycol (As Humectant) were mixed with stirring and allowed hydration for 4-5 hrs for gelling. ME was added in gel phase and left over night for gelling. Finally triethanolamine was added to adjust pH 6. Optimize formula for ME formulation & ME gel are shown in Table 5 & Table 6 respectively.

Characterization:

1. Optimized microemulsion^(16,28,32,33,34,35,36,37)

Qualitative test:-Dilution and Dye solubility tests were performed for determination of type of ME. Transmittance study of ME was done after dilution. Result is shown in Table 7.

Centrifugation test: - This test was used to specify the stability of the microemulsion whether it was monophasic or biphasic. In this, the samples were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 30 minutes and then were examined for whether the system was monophasic or biphasic.

% Assay:- A microemulsion was dissolved in mixture of Methanol: DMSO (2:1), then absorbance was measured at λ_{max} 276 nm by suitable dilution with Methanol: DMSO (2:1). Blank ME was prepared in same manner as discussed in earlier and taken as blank by suitable dilution with Methanol: DMSO (2:1). Result is recorded in Table 8.

pH:- pH of the microemulsion was measured using Systronics 335 pH meter and result is shown in Table 8.

Conductivity measurement:- The conductivity of the microemulsion was measured with Conductometer CM 180 Elico India and result is shown in Table 8.

Viscosity measurement:- The viscosity was determined using Brookfield viscometer (Brookfield engineering laboratory, U.S.A).Results are shown in Table 9.

% Transmittance at 630nm:- The % transmittance was checked against distilled water using UV-visible spectrophotometer at 630 nm (UV, 1601, 220X shimadzu, Japan) and result is shown in Table 8.

Globule size & zeta potential determination:-The globule size & zeta potential were measured with Malvern zetasizer (model Nano ZS, Malvern Instruments, Worcestershire, UK).

Results are shown in Table 8. Graphical presentation of Particle size & zeta potential are shown in Figure 2 & Figure 3 respectively.

2. Optimized microemulsion Gel^(38,39)

% assay:- 200 mg of microemulsion gel was weighed accurately & dissolved in mixture of Methanol: DMSO (2:1), stirred for 5 minutes, absorbance was measured at λ_{max} 276 nm by suitable dilution with Methanol: DMSO (2:1). Blank gel was prepared in same manner as described earlier and taken as blank by suitable dilution with Methanol: DMSO (2:1). Result is recorded in Table 10.

pH:- The pH of microemulsion gel was determined by using Systronics 335 pH meter. One gram of gel was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water and stored for two hours. Result is recorded in Table 10.

Viscosity measurement:- The viscosity was determined using Brookfield viscometer (Brookfield engineering laboratory, U.S.A). Results are shown in Table 10.

In-vitro diffusion study:^(25,40,41,42)

In-vitro study was carried out using cellophane membrane. The cellophane membrane was activated in glycerin for 24 hours. Activated cellophane membrane was mounted on Franz diffusion Cell using Fevi-quick glue at the brim of the donor compartment to avoid leakage of the test sample. The cellophane membrane was placed on the receiver chamber and the donor chamber was clamped in place. The receiver chamber was filled with Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 diffusion medium.

Whole assembly was put on magnetic stirrer. Testing samples were put on the cellophane membrane and stirring was started with note down of time.

Samples were withdrawn from the receiver solution at predetermined time intervals, and the cell was replenished to their marked volumes with fresh buffer solution. Addition of solution to the receiver

compartment was performed with great care to avoid trapping of air.

The samples were filtered from 0.22 μ filter and % drug release was calculated by taking absorbance at λ_{max} 276 nm. For the blank, placebo formulation was carried out for release study for 24 hrs, and that it was processed same way as described above. Comparison of drug release study for Aceclofenac microemulsion, marketed product (Hifenac gel) and microemulsion gel at different time interval are shown in **Table 11**. Graphical presentation of drug release study is shown in **Figure 4**.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Result:-

Solubility Studies: Result of solubility study for different oils, surfactants & cosurfactants are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Aceclofenac solubility study data

Excipients	solubility(mg/ml)
<u>Oil</u>	
Soyabean oil	10.03
Cotton seed oil	8.444
Capmul MCM(C8)	11.23
Isopropyl myristate	15.23
Olive oil	9.834
<u>Surfactant</u>	
Labrafil	17.41
Tween 80	23.74
Creamophore RH	0.1339
<u>Co - surfactant</u>	
Polyethylene glycol 400	221.53
Plurololeique CC 497	18.44

Ternary Phase diagram: surfactants: cosurfactants (4:1) show maximum microemulsion area. So this ratio was selected for further formulation. Phase diagram readings for microemulsion are shown in

Stability study: ^(30, 31, 32)

Optimized microemulsion & microemulsion Gel were subjected to stability study for a period of two months at room temperature and refrigeration condition (2-8°C). During the period of storage the ME was subjected for % transmittance, % assay & pH, while ME gel was subjected for % transmittance, % assay, pH, consistence & viscosity (physical). Results are shown in Table 12, Table 13, Table 14, & Table 15.

Table 2. Figure 1 shows microemulsion area for different ratios of Smix.

Table 2: Phase diagram readings for microemulsion

Sr. No:	Oil :Smix (Ratio)	Oil :Smix (ml)	Dilution with water until microemulsion remains				
			1:1 (s:cos)	2:1 (s:cos)	3:1 (s:cos)	4:1 (s:cos)	5:1 (s:cos)
1	1 : 9	0.3 : 2.7	Infinite	Infinite	Infinite	Infinite	2
2	2 : 8	0.6 : 2.4	5.5	Infinite	Infinite	Infinite	1.8
3	3 : 7	0.9 : 2.1	0.5	0.5	2.0	3.6	1.7
4	4 : 6	1.2 : 1.8	0.30	0.40	1.80	1.8	1
5	5 : 5	1.5 : 1.5	0.25	0.35	0.55	0.80	0.95
6	6 : 4	1.8 : 1.2	0.21	0.32	0.48	0.77	0.68
7	7 : 3	2.1 : 0.9	0.18	0.28	0.45	0.71	0.60
8	8 : 2	2.4 : 0.6	0.16	0.25	0.40	0.64	0.45
9	9 : 1	2.7 : 0.3	0.10	0.20	0.37	0.63	0.35

Figure 1: Pseudoternary phase diagrams of IPM/Tween 80 /PEG 400

Formulation of Microemulsion:**Table 3:** Optimization of microemulsion (Blank batches)

Batch No.	Oil (%)	Smix (%)	Water (%)	% T ($\lambda_{\text{max}}-630\text{nm}$)	Viscosity (Physical observation)
M1	2	30	68	99.6 \pm 0.20	Poor
M2	2	35	63	98.0 \pm 0.28	Very Good
M3	2	40	58	99.4 \pm 0.16	Poor
M4	2	45	53	100.1 \pm 0.10	Good
M5	2	50	48	99.1 \pm 0.23	Poor
M6	4	30	66	96.4 \pm 0.08	Poor
M7	4	35	61	99.2 \pm 0.24	Good
M8	4	40	56	97.9 \pm 0.18	Very Good
M9	4	45	51	99.3 \pm 0.08	Very Good
M10	4	50	46	100.1 \pm 0.11	Poor
M11	6	30	64	---	Poor
M12	6	35	59	94.2 \pm 0.38	Good
M13	6	40	54	99.4 \pm 0.07	Very Good
M14	6	45	49	99.7 \pm 0.08	Very Good
M15	6	50	44	99.6 \pm 0.23	Good
M16	8	30	62	97.9 \pm 0.09	Very good
M17	8	35	57	99.2 \pm 0.28	Poor
M18	8	40	52	99.9 \pm 0.11	Poor
M19	8	45	47	99.5 \pm 0.28	Poor
M20	8	50	42	100.1 \pm 0.21	Good

Table 4: Drug Loaded Microemulsion

Batch No.	IPM (%)	Tween 80: PEG 400 (%)	Water (%)	% Transmittance λ_{\max} -630nm
ACF 1	2	35	63	98.0 \pm 0.28
ACF 2	4	40	56	97.9 \pm 0.18
ACF 3	4	45	51	99.3 \pm 0.08
ACF 4	6	40	54	99.4 \pm 0.07
ACF 5	6	45	49	99.7 \pm 0.08
ACF 6	8	30	62	97.9 \pm 0.90

Optimization formula for microemulsion and microemulsion gel: Optimization formula of microemulsion and microemulsion gel is shown in Table 5 & Table 6 respectively.

Table 5: Composition of final microemulsion

Sr. No.	Ingredient	% w/w
1	Iso-propyl Myristate	6
2	Tween (Surfactant)	80
3	PEG 400 (Co-surfactant)	18
4	Water	49

Table 6: Composition of final microemulsion gel

Sr. No.	Ingredient	% w/w
1	Microemulsion Formulation	94
2	Propylene glycol	4.5
3	Carbopol 934	1.5

Characterization of ME & ME gel:

Qualitative tests:-

Dilution test:- The prepared drug loaded microemulsion was diluted with water and was found to be optically clear.

Dye solubility test:- The water soluble dye was added and was found uniformly distributed throughout the microemulsion without any lump formation.

Centrifugation test:- The microemulsion was found to be optically monophasic even after centrifuging at 10,000 rpm for 30 minutes

Various tests were performed on ME & ME gel. Result of characterization of optimized formulation is shown in Table 7, Table 8, Table 9 & Table 10. Graphical presentation of Particle size & zeta

potential of optimize batch is shown in Figure 2 & Figure 3 respectively.

Table 7: Transmittance study of microemulsion after dilution

Dilution	Transmittance (%)
Undiluted	99.6± 0.06
10	97.9± 0.11
50	96.8± 0.19
100	96.2± 0.34

Table 8: Results of characterization of microemulsion

Test	Optimized drug loaded microemulsion
% Assay	99.1 ± 0.26
pH	5.50 ± 0.19
Conductivity (mS)	0.150 ± 0.11
% Transmittance	99.6± 0.06
Zeta potential (mV)	-4.97 ± 1.1
Globule size (nm)	11.52 ± 0.6
Weight / ml of ME	1.03 gm / ml

Table 9: Viscosity of optimized microemulsion

Viscosity (Cp)	Speed (rpm)	Torque (%)
851.8	0.1	6.1
840.7	0.3	12.2
838.6	0.5	24.3
819.8	0.7	36

Table 10: Results of characterization of microemulsion gel

Test	Observation
% Assay	99.2 ± 0.68
Transparency	Transparent & clear
PH	6.10 ± 0.25
Viscosity	1124 Cp

Figure 2: Particle size of optimized batch

Figure 3: Zeta potential of optimized batch

The Release profile of Aceclofenac:- Satisfactory release profile was found in Microemulsion based preparation compare to the market preparation. Result is shown in Table 11. Graphical presentation of Cumulative % drug release of various formulations is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Graph of % drug release comparison of ME, ME gel and market product of Aceclofenac

Table 11: Cumulative % drug release comparison

Time (hrs)	Microemulsion	Market Product	Microemulsion Gel
1	10.20 ± 0.19	7.20 ± 0.19	9.87 ± 0.08
2	12.68 ± 0.66	8.68 ± 0.66	11.49 ± 1.10
3	14.41 ± 1.40	9.41 ± 1.40	12.21 ± 0.84
4	16.67 ± 1.67	9.67 ± 1.67	12.51 ± 2.64
5	17.85 ± 3.31	15.85 ± 3.31	17.78 ± 3.84
24	22.04 ± 2.12	19.04 ± 2.12	21.88 ± 1.80

% Drug release comparison of ME, ME gel and market product of Aceclofenac (Hifenac gel)

Stability study: Optimize preparations were checked Table 12, Table 13, Table 14, & Table 15. for stability study for 2 months. Results are shown in

Table 12: Results of stability study of microemulsion at room temperature

Test	Time period		
	Initial Reading	1 month	2 months
Transmittance (%)	99.6 ± 0.06	99.6 ± 0.21	99.4 ± 0.18
Assay (%)	99.1 ± 0.26	98.84 ± 0.15	98.82 ± 0.13
pH	5.50 ± 0.19	5.50 ± 0.14	5.50 ± 0.14

Table 13: Results of stability study of microemulsion gel at room temperature

Test	Time period		
	Initial Reading	1 month	2 months
Assay (%)	99.26 ± 0.68	99.22± 0.28	99.20± 0.26
pH	6.10 ± 0.25	5.92 ± 0.38	5.90 ± 0.28
Transparency (Visually)	Transparent & clear	Transparent & clear	Transparent & clear
Consistency	Suitable for application on skin	Suitable for application on skin	Suitable for application on skin
Viscosity	Very good	Very good	Very good

Table 14: Results of stability study of microemulsion at refrigeration temperature

Test	Time period		
	Initial Reading	1 month	2 months
Transmittance (%)	99.9 ± 0.10	99.5 ± 0.09	99.4 ± 0.09
Assay (%)	99.6 ± 0.22	99.1 ± 0.37	99.0 ± 0.37
pH	5.46 ± 0.22	5.44 ± 0.25	5.42 ± 0.20

Table 15: Results of stability study of microemulsion gel at refrigeration temperature

Test	Time period		
	Initial Reading	1 month	2 months
Assay (%)	99.6 ± 2.42	98.9 ± 1.23	98.6 ± 1.13
pH	5.99 ± 0.20	5.99 ± 0.14	5.97 ± 0.12
Transparency (Visually)	Transparent & clear	Transparent & clear	Transparent & clear
Consistency	Suitable for application on skin	Suitable for application on skin	Suitable for application on skin
Viscosity	Very good	Very good	Very good

Discussion:-**Solubility Studies and selection of components**

From solubility study it was found that the solubility of the drug was higher in IPM. So IPM was selected as internal phase for the preparation of microemulsion. Tween 80 & PEG 400 were selected as surfactant & cosurfactant respectively based on solubility study.

Construction of phase diagram

A Pseudoternary phase diagram of the investigated quaternary system water/IPM/Tween 80/PEG 400 was prepared by water titration method. Formation of microemulsion systems (colored area) was observed at room temperature. Phase behavior investigations of this system demonstrated the suitable approach to determining the water phase, oil phase, surfactant concentration and co-surfactant concentration with which the transparent, one phase low-viscous microemulsion system was formed. The phase study revealed that the microemulsion region was found maximum when the surfactant-to-co-surfactant ratio was **4:1**, so this ratio was taken for further study.

Optimization of microemulsion and microemulsion gel

Optimization of microemulsion formulation was done by choosing fixed quantity of oil phase and varying surfactant cosurfactant ratio. Different Batches (Blank) were prepared from M1 to M20. From which

M2, M8, M9, M13, M14 & M16 batches were selected based on their transparency. All these selected batches were prepared with Aceclofenac (ACF 1 to ACF 6) for further characterization. From these batches ACF 5 batch was selected for characterization.

Different concentration of Carbopol 934(0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, 2% & 2.5%), HPMC K4 M (1%, 2% & 3%) and HPMC K100 (1%, 2% & 3%) were taken to prepare ME gel. Among them Carbopol 934 1.5 % gel was optimized based on its viscosity, transparency and its consistency for application on skin.

Characterization of microemulsion and microemulsion gel**Qualitative tests:-**

From the dilution test and dye solubility test the prepared microemulsion was found to be o/w type.

Electro-conductivity, % Transmittance, pH & viscosity:-

As the system was showing conductance, it was proved that the system was o/w type microemulsion preparation. The developed microemulsion showed more than 99% transmittance which proved good transparency of the system. The pH of the microemulsion was found to be 5.50 ± 0.19 which is suitable for application on skin and would not cause any irritation to the skin. Viscosity was found

satisfactory for both microemulsion and microemulsion gel for topical application.

Globule size and zeta potential:-

Globule size of the microemulsions was found to be 11.52 ± 0.6 nm. The nanometric size range of the particle was retained even after 100 times dilution with water which proved the system's compatibility with excess water. Zeta potential was found to be negative charge to the system (-4.97). Hence the formulations will not cause any problem due to electrostatic interaction between the microemulsion and skin on topical administration.

% drug release profile for Aceclofenac:-

In drug release profile, % Aceclofenac released from cellophane paper was found more in Microemulsion ($22.04 \pm 2.12\%$) compared to Microemulsion gel ($21.88 \pm 1.80\%$) and Market Product - Hifenac gel ($19.04 \pm 2.12\%$). which showed drug release from Microemulsion is greater than Microemulsion gel and Market product, but the Microemulsion gel has better consistency for topical drug delivery, for that reason Microemulsion gel was selected for topical drug delivery system.

Stability study:-

Based on visual identification, microemulsion with Aceclofenac remained as clear liquid for a period of two months without the occurrence of phase separation or flocculation at the room temperature and refrigerator temperature. The results of various studies performed on ME & ME gel were found to be satisfactory so both were found to be stable for period of two months.

CONCLUSION

A topical dermatological NSAID's product is designed to deliver drug into the skin in treating pain, where the skin as the target organ. Aceclofenac had poor skin permeability in conventional formulation which is used in topical therapy for the treatment of pain. So, microemulsion was selected as topical formulation to increase skin permeability. In this

investigation, an attempt was made to prepare Aceclofenac loaded microemulsion gel for topical delivery. From this study it is concluded that the microemulsion had been proved to be increased the cutaneous absorption capacity of Aceclofenac. So Microemulsion is found to be powerful formulation for poorly soluble Aceclofenac, for the topical administration.

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